

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW & META-ANALYSIS PROTOCOL

Title of the review	Global prevalence and clinical outcomes of Cryptogenic Cirrhosis: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis
First reviewer	Dr. Anna Sessa
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Declaration of personal and funding interests	None

Support	
SR overview	Dr. Anna Seesa, Dr. Monika Monika Prabhaker-Kaushal, Pr. Maud Lemoine
Protocol development	None
Literature searching	<p>The literature search will be performed independently and in duplicate by Dr Anna Sessa and Dr Monika Prabhaker-Kaushal across the following databases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medline (Ovid) • Embase (Ovid) • Scopus • Web of science • Global health (Ovid) • Global index medicus <p>We will search for original studies (peer-reviewed articles and conference abstracts).</p>

Quality appraisal	<p>We will use a quality score from an appraisal checklist customized from previously published quality assessment tools for prevalence studies (Munn 2015).</p> <p>To assess the risk of bias for study used to evaluate prognosis (only longitudinal studies), we will use the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (Luchini 2017).</p>
Synthesis	<p>We will perform a quantitative synthesis where appropriate.</p> <p>For prevalence outcomes, proportions will be pooled using random-effects models (REML) with variance stabilising transformations (Freeman–Tukey double arcsine or logit), with back-transformation to the proportion scale. We will report pooled estimates with 95% CIs, prediction intervals, and heterogeneity (τ^2, I^2, Q). Prespecified subgroup analyses include clinical setting (e.g., cirrhotic cohorts, LT recipients/candidates, HCC), age group (adult/pediatric), diagnostic method, WHO region, and risk-of-bias strata. Leave-one-out and influence analyses will evaluate robustness.</p> <p>For prognosis, time-to-event effect sizes (adjusted hazard ratios) will be pooled using a random-effects generic inverse-variance model. Where only survival at fixed times is available, we will pool proportions at 1, 5, and 10 years. When needed, $\log(HR)$ and SE will be derived from available statistics/curves using standard methods.</p> <p>Analyses will be conducted in R (packages meta, metafor); if meta-analysis is not feasible, we will provide a structured narrative synthesis.</p>
Writing up	<p>The review will be reported according to PRISMA 2020. We will present: (i) study selection, (ii) characteristics tables, (iii) risk-of-bias summaries, (iv) forest plots and subgroup/meta-regression results, (v) sensitivity and small-study-effect assessments if appropriate, and (vi) key limitations. Where applicable, we will include a Summary of Findings table (prevalence/prognosis) and discuss implications for practice and research. Drafting will follow the CRediT taxonomy (conceptualisation, methodology, investigation, analysis, writing original draft, writing review & editing, supervision). Target journal and authorship order will be agreed a priori; any deviations from protocol will be transparently documented.</p>

1. Background

Cryptogenic cirrhosis (CC) is cirrhosis of unknown aetiology, lacking disease-specific clinical or histological criteria (1). Its global prevalence remains uncertain, with reports ranging from 5 to 30% of cirrhosis cases and nearly 10% of liver transplants (1-3). Over the past four decades, the apparent decline in CC largely reflects improved attribution of previously “idiopathic” liver disease: the discovery of HBV (1965) and HCV (1989) with serology, together with clearer definitions for autoimmune hepatitis and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), reassigned many cases. Before formal NASH guidelines (4-6), ambiguous criteria likely led to misclassification of NASH or burnt-out NASH as CC; in the US registry (1996–2016), CC exceeded 10% until 2004 (when NASH was introduced as a listing diagnosis) and then fell to ~5% (7). Some studies show that patients with late-stage cirrhosis who do not meet definitive steatohepatitis criteria may still display residual histological features of prior NASH on biopsy (1-3,8). The other differential diagnosis includes alcoholic liver disease, NAFLD, viral hepatitis, autoimmune hepatitis, primary biliary cholangitis, and other rare liver conditions. A thorough history, examination, laboratory testing, imaging, and biopsy are essential to distinguish these causes (12). Re-evaluation can uncover missed causes; in one cohort initially labelled CC, a definitive aetiology was identified in ~30% of patients (9).

Additionally, a subset of indeterminate cases may be misattributed to alcohol-related disease or NASH when the clinical picture is equivocal and molecular work-up is incomplete, the converse of the misclassification that prevailed before formal NASH guidelines (4-6). While CC likely aggregates diverse aetiologies, it may also represent a distinct entity that warrants dedicated pathophysiological study; however, evidence remains limited. Approximately 10% of CC cases are discovered incidentally during evaluations for unrelated conditions, such as gallbladder disease (1-3). Nearly 45% of patients present with nonspecific symptoms (e.g., fatigue) or unexplained laboratory abnormalities (1). Many also experience complications of portal hypertension (ascites, encephalopathy, variceal bleeding) (1), and hepatocellular carcinoma can occasionally be the initial presentation (1,4,8,10).

Prognosis may be poorer than for other aetiologies. In one study, mortality was 39.2% over a median 42 months in CC versus 30% in HCV-related cirrhosis; median survival for CC was 60 months (11). Another study reported that CC patients more often had oesophageal varices, lower platelet counts, higher MELD scores, and shorter times to liver-related events than biopsy-proven NASH (12). Overall, data remain limited (11,13-15). Given these gaps, we aim to estimate the global prevalence and prognosis of CC across adult and paediatric populations.

Review questions

1. What is the true prevalence of cryptogenic cirrhosis (CC) among adults with cirrhosis?
2. What is the true prevalence of CC among children?
3. What is the true prevalence of CC in specific subgroups (such as patients with HCC; liver transplant candidates and recipients)?
4. Which factors are associated with CC?
5. What is the prognosis of patients with CC?

Aim

We aim to estimate the real prevalence of cryptogenic cirrhosis and outcomes associated with this disease.

Timeline of Key Developments in HCV and NASH/MASH Identification and Guidelines:

- The first evidence of metabolic steatosis was reported in the 1980s (16). Early studies began to describe liver conditions associated with metabolic factors, although these conditions were not yet formally recognized as distinct entities.
- **1989:** The discovery of the Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) in 1989 (17) was a breakthrough in identifying viral causes of liver disease.
- **1998:** Research led by Yonoussi et al. (18) marked a turning point in the understanding of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH). These studies provided a deeper characterization of non-alcoholic steatohepatitis, distinguishing it from other liver diseases and bringing attention to its clinical significance. This also highlighted the challenge of distinguishing cryptogenic cirrhosis from other aetiologies, such as NASH.
- **2012:** The first AASLD (American Association for the Study of Liver Diseases) guidelines for the management of NASH were published. These guidelines represented the first comprehensive effort to address the diagnosis and treatment of NASH, including its progression to cirrhosis (4).
- **2016:** The first EASL (European Association for the Study of the Liver) guidelines on NASH were released. These guidelines further emphasized the need for accurate identification of NASH, particularly in the context of cirrhosis, as cryptogenic cirrhosis was often confused with advanced NASH (5).
- **2017:** The first NASPGHAN (North American Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology, and Nutrition) guidelines for pediatric NASH were published. These guidelines recognized the growing prevalence of NASH in pediatric populations and provided specific recommendations for diagnosis and management (6).
- **Pre-Guideline Era:** Before the publication of these formal guidelines, cryptogenic cirrhosis was frequently misclassified due to the lack of clear diagnostic criteria for NASH. However, several papers had already recognized NASH as a potential etiology for cirrhosis, particularly in cases where no other cause was identified. These studies paved the way for the formal recognition and integration of NASH/ metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis (MASH) into hepatology practice and they recognized cryptogenic cirrhosis as a distinct entity.

2. Specific objectives

1. To estimate the global prevalence of cryptogenic cirrhosis (CC) in two settings: (I) adult populations with cirrhosis, and (II) paediatric populations assessed in hepatology clinics, including patients evaluated in hepatology services regardless of the underlying liver disease.

2. To describe its geographical distribution and to explore differences according to the method used to diagnose cirrhosis (histological, clinical, radiological, or mixed criteria) and whether CC cases were re-evaluated.
3. To assess the prevalence of CC in specific subgroups, including HCC patients, liver transplant populations (both waiting list and transplanted), and the patients in hepatology clinics, irrespective of cirrhosis status.
4. To evaluate the prognosis of CC-related prognosis by analysing overall survival and adjusted hazard ratios (HRs) from longitudinal studies reporting associations between CC and the risk of death and/or clinical deterioration.
5. To identify factors associated with CC, in particular, to investigate the natural history of cryptogenic cirrhosis, focusing on the progression to decompensated liver failure, the development of cirrhosis-related complications (e.g., ascites, hepatic encephalopathy, variceal bleeding), and the incidence of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC).

3. a) Criteria for including studies in the review

Population, or participants and conditions of interest	<p>Included cohorts reporting CC: hepatocellular carcinoma; liver transplant waiting lists; liver explant series; cohorts of patients with cirrhosis; and hepatology clinic populations irrespective of cirrhosis status (e.g., individuals with chronically abnormal liver tests)</p> <p>There are no restrictions on age, language, type of healthcare facility, or geographical area.</p> <p>Confirmation of cirrhosis will be accepted if any one of the following criteria is met: (i) histology (i.e., liver biopsy); (ii) clinical evidence (e.g., oesophageal varices, ascites) and/or non-invasive tests (e.g., imaging, elastography, or composite scores such as FIB-4); or (iii) mixed criteria (a combination of the above methods).</p> <p>Studies will be excluded if CC was diagnosed in the following populations: Pregnant women, OLT recipients, HIV patients, and individuals with other immunosuppressive conditions</p> <p>Acute liver failure and its causes will not be evaluated.</p> <p>Articles/abstracts without methodological details will be excluded.</p>
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	<p>Reports citing "indeterminate chronic liver disease" or "cryptogenic" without clear documentation of cirrhosis, or with ambiguous definitions of cirrhosis will be excluded.</p> <p>Duplicate cohorts: when multiple publications drew on the same population, we will retain the most complete and/or most recent report.</p>
<p>Interventions or exposures</p>	<p>In this meta-analysis, the exposure refers to patients diagnosed with cryptogenic cirrhosis (CC), defined as cirrhosis with no identifiable aetiology (e.g., viral hepatitis, alcohol-related liver disease, autoimmune hepatitis, or other specific causes). Diagnosis is typically based on clinical, laboratory, imaging, and/or histological findings, with exclusion of other known aetiologies.</p> <p>To ensure consistency and minimise bias, we will use internationally and nationally accepted definitions of CC, as specified in data sources or frameworks such as UNOS (United Network for Organ Sharing) and other relevant national or international guidelines.</p> <p>No specific interventions are considered; however, diagnostic methodologies (e.g., imaging, elastography, liver biopsy) will be extracted and analysed where available.</p> <p>By applying the prespecified eligibility criteria, we aim to refine the analysis and provide a more accurate estimate of the prevalence and characteristics of CC as a distinct entity.</p> <p>The following populations will be excluded: pregnant women, OLT recipients, HIV patients, and individuals with other immunosuppressive conditions.</p> <p>Acute liver failure (ALF) will also be excluded from the scope of this study.</p> <p>Bias Avoidance: NASH/MASH vs Cryptogenic Cirrhosis</p> <p>To avoid bias related to the potential misclassification of NASH/MASH as cryptogenic cirrhosis, specific criteria will be applied:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Papers that did not explicitly include NASH (Non-Alcoholic Steatohepatitis) or MASH (Metabolic Dysfunction-Associated Steatohepatitis) among the aetiologies for liver cirrhosis prior to the publication of relevant guidelines (4-6) will be excluded from the analysis. • UNOS registry analyses published prior to 2004-before the introduction of NASH as an indication in the LT registry-that did not re-evaluate CC cases will be excluded.

	<p>This approach ensures that cryptogenic cirrhosis is not confounded by cases where NASH/MASH was not properly recognized or diagnosed due to the lack of established diagnostic frameworks at the time of publication.</p> <p>An exhaustive etiological work-up (or LT registry data) will be required to document rare liver diseases among cirrhosis cases, at minimum autoimmune hepatitis (AIH), primary biliary cholangitis (PBC), and primary sclerosing cholangitis (PSC) in adults, and genetic cholestasis, metabolic diseases, and biliary atresia in children.</p> <p>By implementing these exclusion criteria, we aim to refine the analysis and provide a more accurate estimation of the prevalence and characteristics of cryptogenic cirrhosis as a distinct entity.</p>
<p>Comparisons or control groups</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>
<p>Outcomes of interest</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Epidemiology and Prevalence <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global prevalence of cryptogenic cirrhosis. • Geographical distribution of CC. 2. Diagnosis and Definitions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevalence of CC confirmed by liver biopsy vs other methods (imaging, laboratory tests, etc.) • Prevalence in studies with case review/re-evaluation vs without case review 3. Clinical Outcomes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disease progression: adjusted hazard ratios (adjusted at least for age, sex, and aetiology) for the association between CC and death and/or clinical deterioration • Incidence of cirrhosis complications (Ascites, Hepatic encephalopathy, Variceal bleeding) and HCC • Overall survival in CC patients or mortality rate. 4. Treatment and Associated Outcomes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of CC patients listed for LT or transplanted. • Proportion of CC patients with HCC or decompensated cirrhosis. <p>Measure of effects: proportion</p> <p>1- Barriers and facilitators</p>

	<p>- Factors associated with cryptogenic cirrhosis</p> <p>Measure of effects Qualitative data</p>
Time frame	<p>Studies from 1989 (1st identification of HCV) to December 2024</p> <p>Note: To provide a more accurate estimation of prevalence, papers that did not explicitly include NASH (Non-Alcoholic Steatohepatitis) or MASH (Metabolic Dysfunction-Associated Steatohepatitis) among the aetiologies for liver cirrhosis prior to the publication of relevant guidelines (4-6) will be excluded from the analysis.</p>
Language	<p>No language restrictions will be applied. Articles published in languages unknown to the study review team will be translated.</p>
Study design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meta-analysis of prevalence-study designs included: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Cohort studies (prospective or retrospective). -Cross-sectional and other longitudinal observational studies. • Meta-analysis of outcomes-study designs included <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Cohort studies with longitudinal follow-up (prospective or retrospective). -Randomized or non-randomized controlled trials (if available). -Case-control studies (if available).

<p>b) Criteria for excluding studies not covered in inclusion criteria</p>
<p>a. Literature reviews, editorials, case reports or case series with less than 10 patients will be excluded. For the meta-analysis of prevalence, randomised controlled trials will be excluded due to lack of representativeness.</p>

<p>1. Search methods</p>

<p>Electronic databases</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medline (Ovid) • Embase (Ovid) • Scopus (Elsevier) • Web of science • Global health (Ovid) • Global index medicus
<p>Search and retrieval of studies</p>	<p>Following deduplication, two reviewers will independently review the list of articles retrieved by the electronic database search, based on title or title and abstract, to identify those meeting the inclusion criteria.</p> <p>If either of the two reviewers considered a study potentially eligible, the full text of this article will be retrieved for further assessment.</p> <p>The retrieved full texts were assessed independently for inclusion by two reviewers.</p> <p>Any disagreements on data will be resolved through discussion with a third reviewer (ML)</p> <p>In cases where data is unclear or missing, the authors of the paper will be contacted.</p>
<p>Search</p>	<p>“(“cirrhosis” OR “liver disease”) AND (“cryptogenic” OR “unknown” OR “undetermined” OR “unexplained”)”</p> <p>Scopus (1989 to December 30, 2024)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. TITLE-ABS-KEY("cirrhosis" OR "liver disease") 2. TITLE-ABS-KEY("cryptogenic" OR "unknown" OR "undetermined" OR "unexplained") 3. 1 AND 2 <hr/> <p>Ovid MEDLINE(R) ALL (1989 to December 30, 2024)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. exp cirrhosis/ 2. exp liver disease/ 3. 1 OR 2

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. exp cryptogenic/ OR exp unknown/ OR exp undetermined/ OR exp unexplained/ 5. (1 OR 2) AND 4
	<p>Embase Classic+Embase (1989 to December 30, 2024)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. exp cirrhosis/ 2. exp liver disease/ 3. 1 OR 2 4. exp cryptogenic/ OR exp unknown/ OR exp undetermined/ OR exp unexplained/ 5. (1 OR 2) AND 4
	<p>Global Health (1989 to December 30, 2024)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (Cirrhosis).mp. 2. (Liver disease).mp. 3. (Cryptogenic OR unknown OR undetermined OR unexplained).mp. 4. (1 OR 2) AND 3
	<p>Web of Science (1989 to December 30, 2024)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. TS=("cirrhosis") 2. TS=("liver disease") 3. TS=("cryptogenic" OR "unknown" OR "undetermined" OR "unexplained") 4. (1 OR 2) AND 3
	<p>Global Index Medicus (1989 to December 30, 2024)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. cirrhosis 2. liver disease 3. cryptogenic OR unknown OR undetermined OR unexplained 4. (1 OR 2) AND 3

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1. Methods of review	
Details of methods	<p>Two main reviewers and a third to resolve any disagreements were engaged.</p> <p>Main reviewers are Dr. Anna Sessa and Dr. Monika Prabahker, the third reviewer is Pr. Lemoine.</p> <p>Covidence will be used to remove duplicates.</p>
Quality assessment	<p>-Munn Z, Moola S, Lisy K, Riitano D, Tufanaru C. Methodological guidance for systematic reviews of observational epidemiological studies reporting prevalence and cumulative incidence data. <i>International Journal of Evidence-Based Healthcare</i> 2015;13:147–53. https://doi.org/10.1097/XEB.0000000000000054.</p> <p>-Luchini C, Stubbs B, Solmi M, Veronese N. Assessing the quality of studies in meta-analyses: Advantages and limitations of the Newcastle Ottawa Scale. <i>WJMA</i> 2017;5:80. https://doi.org/10.13105/wjma.v5.i4.80.</p>
Data extraction	<p>Data will be extracted using a pre-designed template to capture all required fields for analysis (Data extraction form).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviewer 1 (Dr Anna Sessa) will perform the primary data extraction.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviewer 3 (Prof Maud Lemoine) will check the extracted data against the source reports for accuracy and completeness <p>Fields to be extracted</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Study identification and methods: first author, year, country, WHO region, funding, study design (prospective/retrospective; longitudinal/cross-sectional), data-collection period, recruitment method, aetiological work-up. 2. Population and cohort type: adults/children; specific cohort (HCC, LT waiting list, LT explants, cirrhotic cohort, hepatology clinic populations irrespective of cirrhosis status). 3. Diagnostics: method used to diagnose cirrhosis (histological, clinical, radiological, or mixed); whether case re-evaluation was performed. 4. Baseline characteristics: total sample size, number with CC, age (mean/median), sex distribution. 5. CC characteristics and clinical outcomes: age (mean/median), sex distribution, comorbidities (e.g., diabetes, BMI where reported), ascites, variceal bleeding, HCC, encephalopathy, mortality rate (at baseline and during follow-up, if reported). 6. Prognosis outcomes (if reported): outcomes assessed (e.g., mortality, liver transplantation, decompensation), effect measures (HR/RR/OR with 95% CI), follow-up duration (median/mean), adjustment variables, number of events, overall survival at specified time point(s).
<p>Narrative synthesis</p>	<p>A meta-analysis of proportions or a meta-regression to look at study-level covariates associated with outcomes will be used if appropriate.</p> <p>A narrative synthesis will be conducted using a framework consisting of four elements:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) estimating the global prevalence of CC and describing its geographical distribution; b) developing a preliminary synthesis of findings from the included studies; c) exploring relationships within and across studies; d) assessing the robustness of the synthesis.

2. Presentation of results	
Additional material	PRISMA flow chart, Summary table, Quantitative synthesis of studies evaluating the real prevalence of cryptogenic cirrhosis and its associated factors
Outputs from review	<p>Conferences:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AASLD Liver meeting 2024 2. EASL 2024 <p>Target journals:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lancet Gastroenterology and Hepatology 2. Journal of Hepatology

3. Timeline for the review (6 months)	
protocol	1 month
Literature searching	1 months
Study selection	1 months
Quality appraisal	1 months
Data extraction	2 months
synthesis	1 months
Writing up	1 months

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